

Management Level Security in E-Commerce and Biometric Technology

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ABSTRACT

It is clear that electronic commerce will revolutionize businesses, and customers will be offered new and exciting services. As E-commerce businesses are growing, more secure technologies are being developed and improved every day. The current internet security polices and technologies fail to meet the needs of end users. Enterprises must provide secure services for their customers in e-commerce. There are some threats that should consider in this area. Providing secure services is so extensive and difficult, using the appropriate techniques can facilitate implementing. Here we try to introduce a management level security and biometric technology in e-commerce which includes security standards and protocols. In this paper, it is highlights how biometric technology is beneficial for management level security in e-commerce.

Keywords – biometric technology; e-commerce security; e-commerce protocols

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1. Introduction

E-commerce is buying and selling of goods and services across the internet. Commercial activities over the internet have been growing in an exponential manner over the last few years. When it comes to payment, one needs to establish a sense of security [1], [2]. A good definition of electronic commerce would mention the use of electronic data transmission to implement or enhance any business process. IBM has defined electronic business to be “the transformation of key business processes through the use of Internet technologies [3]. An electronic payment transaction is an execution of a protocol by which amount of money is taken from a payer and given to a payee. [4] E-Commerce is a growing phenomenon as consumers gain experience and comfort with shopping on the Internet. E-commerce offers lower transactions cost, more timely execution and improved market efficiency. Benefit includes increased trade, a wealthier society and a more equitable distribution. [5] Some problems in this field are as following: Insufficient security to prevent hacking and viruses, Sales and marketing requires high human interaction, insufficient security for on-line credit payment transaction, and Cost of setting up of E-Commerce is high.[6] lack of assurance about security is the greatest barrier currently affecting the growth of ecommerce. Consumers must have confidence that their electronic transactions will remain private and unaltered. They must trust the system to prevent fraud and keep their transactions private. Businesses require assurance that their systems and digital assets will remain safe from security intrusions, sabotage, and fraud. For e-commerce to reach its potential confidence in the security of the system must be assured [5] security problems arise unceasingly, and bring a lot of potential security problems for ecommerce transactions. So, security is often cited as a major barrier to the further development of Ecommerce, and it is a problem which we should overcome and pay attention to [7]. The organizations were reluctant to use E-commerce as they felt that the transactions conducted electronically were open to hackers and viruses, which are beyond their control. They were also skeptical about the security measures that were implemented to safeguard on-line payment transactions [6]. Any individual, business or commercial institutions and banks will not do business transactions through an insecure network, which will lead to commercial secrets or personal privacy information leakage, resulting in huge loss of profits. The core issue of e-commerce is security [8]. Integrity mechanisms ensure that other parties do not intercept or alter e-payment information. This can be achieved via the use of encryption mechanisms, including Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) and Secure Electronic Transaction (SET) technologies [9]. In this paper we try to introduce a management level security and biometric technology in e-commerce. In the management level we chose ISO/IEC as the best management standard [10], and in the technical level we use SET, SSL, the advantage of this paper is that it covers areas such as software security, hardware security, physical security, business continuity and etc. We express related protocols in the next section then we discuss about the technology with solutions for threats at management level.

2. E-Commerce Security in the Management Level

It is clear that electronic commerce will revolutionize businesses, and customers will be offered new and exciting services. As E-commerce businesses are growing, more secure technologies are being developed and improved every day. The current internet security polices and technologies fail to meet the needs of end users. The success or failure of an E-commerce operations hinges on myriad factors, including but not limited to the business model, the team, the customers, the investors, the product, and the security of data transmissions and storage. Any business that wants to have a competitive edge in today's global marketplace should adopt a comprehensive security policy in consultation with partners, suppliers, and distributors that will provide safe environment for the coming proliferation of E-commerce [2]. The variables as encryption, protection, verification, and authentication should be the antecedents of perceived security, which influence the perceived security of consumers [11]. E-commerce can be divided in two levels: management and technical level. Management level includes all the organization related parts such as human security, physical security, business continuity and etc. In the management level, following areas should be considered [12].

1. Security policy
2. Organization of information security
3. Asset management
4. Physical and environmental security
5. Communications and operations management
6. Access control
7. Information systems development and maintenance
8. Information Security Incident Management
9. Business continuity

3. The Threats to E-Commerce in the Management Level

There are some threats to e-commerce systems, and it's necessary to understand these threats. The following paragraph contains these threats in management level. In the management level we have the risk of, war, theft, fire, natural disasters, distance from emergency services and etc. Basic security measures will depend on the operational location of the organization [13]. ISO/IEC 27005:2008 have listed these threats, some of them that relates to e-commerce are listed:

Typical threats:

1. Physical damage
2. Loss of essential services
3. Compromise of information

4. Technical failures

5. Unauthorized actions

Human threats:

1. Computer criminal

2. Industrial espionage

3. Insiders (poorly trained, disgruntled, malicious, negligent, dishonest, or terminated employees)

Figure 1

4. E-Commerce Security Protocols

There are different protocols used for ecommerce from secure web to secure payment. Some of the most commonly used protocols have been expressed in the following subsections.

4.1. ISO/IEC 27001:2005

In the management level we chose ISO/IEC 27001:2005 as the best management standard. ISO/IEC 27001:2005 is directly related to the original BS-7799. The basic premise of the original standard still remains, though its implementation and management requirements have been updated to address current security concerns. The number of controls defined in ISO-

27001:2005 has increased to 133 from the original 127 controls defined in BS-7799, due primarily to the inclusion of an 11th control area, Information Security Incident Management. This standard uses PDCA process that contains plan, Do, Check, Act [14].

4.2. Secure Sockets Layer (SSL)

SSL is a security protocol that protects communications between any SSL enabled client and server software running on a network. SSL approach to add layer between the network transport protocol and the application. Data is encrypted before transmission and decrypted before it can be used by the receiving system [14]. SSL remarkably increases the computation time necessary to serve a connection, this increment has a noticeable impact on the server's performance, which has been evaluated. The SSL protocol by combination of public and private key and digital certificates can provide communication privacy (X.509).

4.3. Secure Electronic Transactions (SET)

It is a standardized industry wide protocol specification designated to secure payment transactions and authenticate the parties involved in the transaction in any type of networks including Internet. VISA and MasterCard developed the SET standard with collaboration from leading software companies such as Microsoft, Netscape, RSA, VeriSign, and other. SET was created to provide the trust needed for consumers. The protocol uses cryptography and digital certificates to provide confidentiality of the information, ensure payment integrity, identity, legitimacy and anti-repudiation and authenticate merchants, banks, and cardholders during SET transaction [15],[16]. SET retain customer credit card under the premise of certification, but also increased its business identity authentication, for the need to pay in terms of currency trading is essential. SET will be able to establish a safe use of Internet, bank cards standards. The SET protocol using a dual signatures to ensure that all participants of information isolated from each other, so that businesses can only see the cardholder ordering the data, while banks can only obtain the cardholder's credit card information. [16]

5. Security Directions for E-Commerce Applications

Various aspects of security are relevant to e-commerce. These include database security, in particular federated database security, workflow security, role based access control and e-commerce security at management level. Various efforts have been reported in [17], [18].It described end-to-end security including security for clients and servers as well as transactions. One of the key issues here is how do you protect your assets while collaborating with other organizations.

5.1 Access Control Policies for E-Commerce

Various policies are needed to ensure that users access only the information they are authorized to. Although several efforts have been made [19] in the development of access control models for traditional database environments, the e-commerce environment is quite different from traditional database environments for which such models have been specified. The main difference is that e-commerce requires the ability to specify access control policies more expressive than those provided in traditional DBMSs. In conventional database environments access control is usually performed against a set of authorizations stated by security officers or users according to some security policies. An authorization in general is specified on the basis of three parameters $\langle U, O, p \rangle$. This triple specifies that user U is authorized to exercise privilege p on object O . Such simple paradigm is not well suited for a dynamic environment like e-commerce that requires re-visiting of such paradigm. Furthermore, in an e-commerce environment the resources to be protected are not only traditional data but also knowledge and expertise. Such peculiarities call for more flexibility in specifying access control policies. The access control mechanism must be flexible enough to support a wide spectrum of heterogeneous protection objects. A second related requirement is the support for content-based access control. Content-based access control allows one to express access control policies that take the protection object content into account. This is an important requirement since very often protection objects with the same type and structure have contents of different sensitivity degrees. In order to support content-based access control, access control policies must allow one to include conditions against protection object content. A third requirement is related to the heterogeneity of subjects which requires access control policies based on user characteristics and qualifications, rather than based on very specific and individual characteristics (e.g., user IDs). A possible solution, to better take into account user profiles in the formulation of access control policies, is to support the notion of credential. A credential is a set of properties concerning a user that are relevant for security purposes (for example, age, position within an organization, projects a user is working on). The use of credentials allows the security officer to directly express relevant security policies in terms that are closer to the organizational structure.

6. Biometric Security

The security field uses three different types of authentication:

- Something you know—a password, PIN, or piece of personal information (such as your mother's maiden name)
- Something you have—a card key, smart card, or token (like a Secure ID card)
- Something you are—a biometric. Of these, a biometric is the most secure and convenient authentication tool. It can't be borrowed, stolen, or forgotten, and forging one is practically impossible. Biometrics measure individuals' unique physical or behavioral characteristics are to recognize and authenticate their identity. Common physical biometrics include fingerprints;

hand or palm geometry; and retina, iris, or facial characteristics. Behavioral characters include signature, voice (which also has a physical component), keystroke pattern, and gait. Of this class of biometrics, technologies for signature and voice are the most developed [20][21][22].

6.1 Fingerprints

A fingerprint looks at the patterns found on a fingertip. There are a variety of approaches to fingerprint verification. Some emulate the traditional police method of matching minutiae; others use straight pattern-matching devices; and still others are a bit more unique, including things like moiré fringe patterns and ultrasonics. Some verification approaches can detect when a live finger is presented; some cannot. A greater variety of fingerprint devices is available than for any other biometric. As the prices of these devices and processing costs fall, using fingerprints for user verification is gaining acceptance—despite the common-criminal stigma. Fingerprint verification may be a good choice for in house systems, where you can give users adequate explanation and training, and where the system operates in a controlled environment. It is not surprising that the workstation access application area seems to be based almost exclusively on fingerprints, due to the relatively low cost, small size, and ease of integration of fingerprint authentication devices.

6.2 Hand Geometry

Hand geometry involves analyzing and measuring the shape of the hand. This biometric offer a good balances of performance characteristics and is relatively easy to use. It might be suitable where there are more users or where users access the system infrequently and are perhaps less disciplined in their approach to the system. Accuracy can be very high if desired and flexible performance tuning and configuration can accommodate a wide range of applications. Organizations are using hand geometry readers in various scenarios, including time and attendance recording, where they have proved extremely popular. Ease of integration into other systems and processes, coupled with ease of use, and makes hand geometry an obvious first step for many biometric projects.

6.3 Retina

A retina-based biometric involves analyzing the layer of blood vessels situated at the back of the eye. An established technology, this technique involves using a low intensity light source through an optical coupler to scan the unique patterns of the retina. Retinal scanning can be quite accurate but does require the user to look into a receptacle and focus on a given point. This is not particularly convenient if you wear glasses or are concerned about having close contact with the reading device. For these reasons, retinal scanning is not warmly accepted by all users, even though the technology itself can work well.

6.4 Iris

An iris-based biometric, on the other hand, involves analyzing features found in the colored ring of tissue that surrounds the pupil. Iris scanning, undoubtedly the less intrusive of the eye related biometrics, uses a fairly conventional camera element and requires no close contact between the user and the reader. In addition, it has the potential for higher than average template- matching performance. Iris biometrics work with glasses in place and is one of the few devices that can work well in identification mode. Ease of use and system integration has not traditionally been strong points with iris scanning devices, but you can expect improvements in these areas as new products emerge.

6.5 Face

Face recognition analyzes facial characteristics. It requires a digital camera to develop a facial image of the user for authentication. This technique has attracted considerable interest, although many people don't completely understand its capabilities. Some vendors have made extravagant claims—which are very difficult, if not impossible, to substantiate in practice—for facial recognition devices. Because facial scanning needs an extra peripheral not customarily included with basic PCs, it is more of a niche market for network authentication. However, the casino industry has capitalized on this technology to create a facial database of scam artists for quick detection by security personnel.

6.6 Voice

Voice authentication is not based on voice recognition but on voice-to-print authentication, where complex technology transforms voice into text. Voice biometrics has the most potential for growth, because it requires no new hardware—most PCs already contain a microphone. However, poor quality and ambient noise can affect verification. In addition, the enrollment procedure has often been more complicated than with other biometrics, leading to the perception that voice verification is not user friendly. Therefore, voice authentication software needs improvement. One day, voice may become an additive technology to finger-scan technology. Because many people see finger scanning as a higher authentication form, voice biometrics will most likely be relegated to replacing or enhancing PINs, passwords, or account names.

Figure 2

7. Uses for Biometrics in E-Commerce

Security systems use biometrics for two basic purposes: to verify or to identify users. Identification tends to be the more difficult of the two uses because a system must search a database of enrolled users to find a match (a one-to-many search). The biometric that a security system employs depends in part on what the system is protecting and what it is trying to protect against. E-commerce developers are exploring the use of biometrics and smart cards to more accurately verify a trading party's identity. For example, many banks are interested in this combination to better authenticate customers and ensure nonrepudiation of online banking, trading, and purchasing transactions. Point-of-sales (POS) system vendors are working on the cardholder verification method, which would enlist smart cards and biometrics to replace signature verification. MasterCard estimates that adding smart-card-based biometric authentication to a POS credit card payment will decrease fraud by 80 percent. Some are using biometrics to obtain secure services over the telephone through voice authentication. Developed by Nuance Communications, voice authentication systems are currently deployed nationwide by both the Home Shopping Network and Charles Schwab. The latter's marketing catch phrase is "No PIN to remember, no PIN to forget."

8. Conclusion

As E-commerce businesses are growing, more secure technologies are being developed and improved every day. The current internet security polices and technologies fail to meet the needs of end users. Enterprises must provide secure services for their customers in e-commerce. There are some threats that should consider in this area. Providing secure services is so

extensive and difficult, using the appropriate techniques can facilitate implementing. Here we try to introduce a management level security and biometric technology in e-commerce which includes security standards and protocols. The aim of this paper is to express the solution of e-commerce at technical level using protocols and new technologies like biometric and watermarking technologies.

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